

STRATEGIC PLAN

2021-2025

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Citizen Science Lab, Leiden University
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**citizen
science
lab**

Strategic Plan of the Citizen Science Lab at Leiden University

Executive Summary

The Citizen Science Lab brings together scientists, policy makers, citizens, and other stakeholders in participatory research projects that address scientific questions and/or urgent societal issues that can only be solved by actively involving volunteers in the scientific process. In order to achieve this, the Citizen Science Lab (CSLab) acts as a facilitator and incubator to co-create new citizen science projects that connect society with science. The CSLab also functions as a knowledge hub to build a collaborative and transdisciplinary knowledge-sharing network for citizen science practices in Leiden and across the Netherlands.

“When looking to the future, we envision universities without walls; these are **universities that are open and engaged in society** while retaining their core values.” - A Vision for 2030, European University Association

It is our ambition to build on the foundation that we have already established and expand and consolidate our role as the central hub for expertise and innovation in citizen science for all Faculties of Leiden University, in collaboration with the inhabitants of Leiden and the surrounding region.

Immediate opportunities for the CSLab to seize include delivering the PARTICIPATE programme and ‘Festival of *Citizen Science*’ activities as part of European City of Science Leiden 2022; and becoming a cornerstone of the National Citizen Science Network in the Netherlands and one of the European powerhouses for Citizen Science

Our concrete aims for the next 2 years are to:

- Establish the Citizen Science Lab Knowledge Hub and Project Incubator for Citizen Science at Leiden University and the rest of the municipality of Leiden.
- Support and co-develop CS projects within the University and local communities.
- Lead and implement citizen science activities for European City of Science - Leiden 2022.
- Launch one large ‘radically co-created’ flagship project in the context of the SDGs.
- Fully integrate citizen science practices into the University’s research structure and educational programmes.
- Become an internationally recognised knowledge hub and research centre for the ‘science of citizen science’, co-creation, and transdisciplinary practices.
- Build up a diverse and sustainable portfolio of innovative citizen science projects.

Our Mission is to be a Leiden Knowledge Hub & Project Incubator for Citizen Science

Citizen science engages the public and other stakeholders in participatory scientific research that generates new knowledge, informs decision making, and leads to policy changes that address a range of relevant societal challenges (such as Climate Change, and the UN Sustainable Development Goals). Such ambitious research objectives require a truly transdisciplinary approach to bring researchers from different fields together in collaboration with stakeholders who have practical expertise, and citizens who have local and traditional knowledge. The real promise of citizen science lies in achieving value for all participants, in alignment towards a shared objective - stepping beyond science communications and public dialogue into genuine participation across the entire research journey. The pioneering co-creation method developed by the Citizen Science Lab (CSLab) actively connects the “top-down” approach from academia with the “bottom-up” up approach from society to achieve shared objectives in partnership together. This not only strengthens both engagement and impact, but also opens up new fields of application for citizen science.

The mission of the CSLab is to be the Knowledge Hub, Project Incubator, and Research Centre for citizen science in Leiden and the Netherlands. Experience in applying citizen science approaches is currently scattered across the University (and is similarly scattered in small pockets across the Netherlands), where it risks remaining stuck in silos. Centrally pooling this knowledge and experience not only enriches it with new insights and progression of the state-of-the-art, but also fosters a more transdisciplinary approach that can greatly heighten the quality of the research and its value to both science and society. Furthermore, by building capacity for co-creation, co-design, and multi-stakeholder collaboration, a better balance of bottom-up and top-down approaches can be achieved, such that local and traditional knowledge is represented, and local needs, practices and culture are taken into account - once again greatly heightening the quality of the research and its value to both science and society.

OUR VISION: In 2025, Leiden is a pioneer of citizen science that is initiated and carried out jointly by the University and the rest of the city to address urgent scientific and societal challenges.

The CSLab brings together scientific and societal partners, facilitates the co-creation process and stakeholder engagement, provides advice regarding citizen science strategies, supports projects through to a pilot/prototyping stage, performs evaluations of project goals, and helps projects to achieve sustainable funding and structural implementation. The CSLab collaborates with researchers at other universities to mainstream citizen science practices across the Netherlands. And at the European level, the CSLab leads on the ‘Science of Citizen Science’ as CS Principal Investigator in transdisciplinary consortia responding to the aims of the

European Green Deal, the EU Missions, and the Horizon Europe Programme.

The CSLab explicitly covers all Leiden University research fields - the natural sciences, social sciences, humanities, and the arts - and brings them together in transdisciplinary approaches. The CSLab connects with these areas of subject-matter expertise via our Scientific Core Group, who serve as advisors, ambassadors, and collaboration partners of the Lab within every Faculty of the University. The Scientific Core Group will be extended to also encompass the eight interdisciplinary 'Stimulerings' programmes launched in 2020.

Our Founding Story

The Citizen Science Lab at Leiden University was founded in 2018 by researchers in the Leiden Observatory and Science Communication & Society Department in order to consolidate and build on the knowledge gained in practice from the planning and execution of the iSPEX, Dark Sky Meter, Grote Griepmeting, and Schone Rivieren citizen science projects.

The first activity of the CSLab was to organize an international workshop at the Lorentz Center at Leiden University, which brought together 55 scientists and non-scientists to co-create breakthrough citizen science projects for measuring, understanding, and mitigating air pollution. This led to new collaborative relationships and the submission of two funding proposals to the EU Horizon 2020 'Science with and for Society' programme (not funded). Subsequent co-creation workshops at the Lorentz Center have focused on Sampling Language and Culture, and Archaeology (which led to the Erfgoed Gezocht project).

plastic spotter

For the 444th anniversary of the University in 2019, the CSLab developed a pioneering 'radical co-creation' method for residents across the whole city to collaborate with scientists in research projects that address local societal issues and scientific questions. This resulted in the launch of two winning projects - [Plastic Spotter](#) and [Psychology Lab on Wheels](#) - out of 55 CS ideas submitted by citizens and academics of Leiden and Den Haag. Local funding for this project allowed us to cover the cost of a part-time Community Manager within the CSLab to manage the project, who has now gone on to start a PhD on the topic of citizen science approaches for addressing plastic pollution.

eu-citizen.science

The CSLab successfully leveraged the tool developed for the iSPEX project into ongoing funding for developing its application for optical water quality monitoring in the EU Horizon 2020 funded project [Monocle](#). This work has been built on further in a joint proposal for European Green Deal funding, currently outstanding. The CSLab has also brought in funding for a 0.2 Community Manager within the CSLab via the EU Horizon 2020 projects: [ScienceShops.eu](#) and [EU-Citizen.Science](#), both of which have been laying the groundwork for the further growth of the CSLab.

01 **GOAL 1:** Establish a Leiden University knowledge hub and project incubator for citizen science

02 **GOAL 2:** Design and implement the citizen science programme for the 2022 European City of *(Citizen)* Science.

03 **GOAL 3:** Launch a flagship initiative to 'radically co-create' CS projects for the SDGs

04 **GOAL 4:** Embed CS practices into education, research and societal activities within Leiden and the surrounding region, for the long term

05 **GOAL 5:** Establish the CSLab as a cornerstone of the nascent Dutch National Platform for Citizen Science

Our Strategic Goals for the Citizen Science Lab

GOAL 1: Establish a Leiden University knowledge hub and project incubator for citizen science

Ever since its founding in 1575, Leiden University has had a large influence on both science and society. In the 2010 strategic plan for 'Inspiration and Growth', the University emphasised reaching out more internationally and raising both academic and research achievement. This was built on further in the 2015 strategic plan for 'Freedom to Excel', with an additional focus on innovation and greater impact. As the University now heads into the next strategic planning cycle, the world has changed a great deal, and the current vision for a safe, healthy, sustainable, prosperous and fair world is likely to become even more important. The University of Leiden plays a more vital role than ever to deliver on this vision for both science and society, but in order to do so, it must engage much more deeply with society and societal issues.

Citizen science approaches are one key to achieving this, and pockets of experience are already scattered across the faculties. The CSLab will unite these in one central knowledge hub to further develop both expertise and capacity, building a portfolio of citizen science projects that are incubated and launched in Leiden. We will support colleagues across the University in embedding citizen engagement and 'burgerparticipatie' within their research practices

(particularly in conjunction with funding proposals where this is a requirement). And we will build on thought leadership such as 'The Quality Factors of Citizen Science' and 'The Characteristics of Citizen Science' to provide guidance, coordination and advice for citizen science initiatives within the University, in partnership with external stakeholders and residents. In the European context, the CSLab will join and coordinate ambitious EU research proposals and projects, representing 'the Science of Citizen Science' in transdisciplinary consortia.

SMART Objectives: By 31/12/2021 increase the CSLab mailing list from 165 to 300 recipients; successfully maintain the monthly CS Webinar series with a 50:50 mix of internal/external and Dutch/English sessions; run one bespoke 'Introduction to the CSLab and the 10 Principles of Citizen Science' workshop within each faculty of the University (building on the successful workshop for the Socio-Linguistics department); publish a Guidance document for the Quality Factors of Citizen Science in both English and Dutch; co-write at least one citizen science project proposal with Margaret Gold as Co-Investigator in response to the NWO Open Science Fund call to "stimulate wider adoption of Open Science practices among researchers, for example by promoting wide uptake or implementation of existing tools or ways of working, or by facilitating exchange of practice through training activities or by developing communities around existing Open Science tools and platforms", with submission deadline April 1, 2021 with a total maximum value of €50,000; and co-write at least one citizen science project proposal (each) in response to the Horizon Europe call for "Kick-starting and making citizen science initiatives sustainable in the European Research Area", and for "A capacity-building and brokering network to make citizen science an integral part of the European Research Area" (not yet open)

GOAL 2: Design and implement the 'Participate' programme for the 2022 European City of (Citizen) Science.

In 2022, Leiden will be the European City of Science and host of the EuroScience Open Forum conference, and all eyes will be on the Netherlands. EuroScience has already set the bar

high - the City of Science programme should “go above and beyond the normal scientific outreach and networking activities” to “enable connections with non-scientists” and clearly express what the “expected outcomes of those connections” are. Stichting Leiden 2022 has responded by launching an ambitious programme of activities to engage ‘101 neighbourhoods’ in the themes of Contemplate - Participate - Celebrate throughout the year-long European Science in the City Festival.

The CSLab has been invited to propose a comprehensive citizen science programme within the ‘PARTICIPATE’ track of the programme. Our vision for the Participate programme is to put together a yearlong ‘Festival of Citizen Science’, with a flagship ‘Citizen Science for the SDGs’ project at its heart (see Goal 3), and a portfolio of citizen science projects related to the scientific themes that people can participate in, and projects with direct relevance to the neighbourhoods, i.e., ‘Kennis voor en door de Wijken’. Within this, it is our ambition to originate and launch 3 to 5 new initiatives in partnership with researchers at the University to more closely engage residents in a diverse range of research.

This ‘Participate’ programme will be underpinned by the Leiden 2022 ‘Participate Platform, which will showcase all of the engagement opportunities throughout the festival and become a permanent platform for citizen science across the entire region after 2022. Our ambition is to extend this platform to also support the National CS network (see Goal 5) such that it becomes a permanent portal for citizen science initiatives and other forms of science engagement across the Netherlands, beyond 2022.

SMART Objectives: By 31/03/2021 secure formal partnership in ECS22 and agree on the 'Participate' mandate; by 31/12/2021 identify and build a portfolio of existing citizen science projects to match the scientific themes of Leiden 2022 (minimum 9, maximum 20) in collaboration with UL colleagues (via the Scientific Core Group and the ECS22 Steering Committee) and our network of CS practitioners in the Netherlands; originate and launch at least one (and a maximum of 5) locally situated CS project(s) that are relevant to the neighbourhoods of Leiden to deliver a 'kennis voor & door de wijken' element of the programme; design and deliver the City of Citizen Science Festival programme that weaves these CS projects into the '365 nieuwsgierigmakende kennis onderwerpen' of the 101 Neighbourhoods programme; by 31/03/2021 identify the best platform functionality + partnership to underpin the Participate Platform, agree on KPIs with Stichting LECS22, design and develop the 'white-labelled' platform for Leiden 2022, and launch with full portfolio of CS projects by 31/12/2021; identify and secure a physical location to establish a 'Participate' Locket within the city centre, to become a permanent location for Citizen Science engagement and events beyond 2022 (in alignment where possible with the aims to establish a 'Huis van Wetenschap' and 'New Leiden Bauhaus').

GOAL 3: Launch a flagship initiative to 'radically co-create' CS projects that address the UN SDGs

The flagship project of the Citizen Science Lab will be to launch two or more large-scale 'Citizen Science for the SDGs' projects that address the UN Sustainable Development Goals in the local context - in active collaboration with researchers at the University, residents of Leiden and the surrounding region, and other local stakeholders.

This initiative will build on the pioneering 'radical co-creation' methodology first developed for the 444th anniversary celebration and invite all residents of the city and surrounding region to propose a research question to investigate together towards achieving the Global Goals, which will be selected and co-developed through a series of collaborative stakeholder events and co-creation workshops. This process will lead to the launch of at least

two Leiden-based citizen science projects during Leiden 2022, which can be showcased at the ESOF conference as evidence of 'citizen science in action', and will culminate in the creation of a Leiden SDGs dashboard.

The 'CS for the SDGs' project team will consist of the Coordinator and citizen science experts within the CSLab who will incubate the project and facilitate the process, and the Scientific Core Group made up of individual researchers from all University Faculties who will support the further development of the scientific research questions that emerge, and the development of the research approach. This will strengthen transdisciplinary ties across the whole University, as well as with

stakeholders in Leiden and across the region. The emergent national CS network will provide the opportunity to scale this initiative up to the national level.

We have chosen to frame this initiative in the context of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) based on the strategic ambition of the University to strengthen its impact towards a safe, healthy, sustainable, prosperous and just world. The SDGs provide an excellent framework of urgent and interconnected scientific and societal challenges that require the transdisciplinary collaboration of scientists and scholars, together with society-at-large. Citizen science can play a vital role in helping to monitor and achieve the targets set within each of these goals by making a direct contribution to the underlying indicators.

This project will leverage expertise and knowledge across the University to deliver relevant scientific and societal impact and establish a lasting transdisciplinary structure for future research collaborations. The learning and outcomes of the project will be showcased at the EuroScience Open Forum (ESOF) 2022 conference, and Leiden European City of Science events.

SMART Objectives: By 31/12/2021 launch call for questions; target reach for communicating the 'CS for SDGs' initiative = 2000; target number of research question submissions = 55; Over 2022 the target number of participants in collaborative sessions (aggregate) = 800; target social media reach = 3000; projects selected, developed and launched = 2-4 (depending on funding available to support and criteria met); target number of participants in the CS projects (aggregate) = 1500; by 31/12/2022 Leiden SDGs dashboard is launched.

GOAL 4: Embed CS practices into education, research and societal activities within Leiden and the surrounding region, for the long term

It is our ambition to build long-term operational infrastructure for citizen science in Leiden that is based at the University but outward facing towards society and the surrounding region, to embed CS practices within all areas of scientific research in Leiden, and to build community capacity for CS in collaboration with residents, policy makers and other societal stakeholders. This ambition draws on both the 'doing' and 'thinking' sides of the CSLab equation. As a CS Project Incubator, we will support the project development process with facilitation, advice, mentoring, proto-typing, stakeholder engagement and community building,

partnering, coordination, and other project services. As a CS Knowledge Hub, we will build and develop capacity for CS as a practice by delivering training and workshops, developing resources and guidelines, researching best practice, furthering the state of the art in transdisciplinary collaborations, and building CS education into the curriculum. Underpinning both, the CSLab will build a collaborative and transdisciplinary knowledge-sharing network for citizen science practices across the region, and the rest of the Netherlands.

To support this, the CSLab will be staffed with a full-time Coordinator, project managers & community managers who lead the involvement of the CSLab in collaborative CS projects, researchers furthering innovation in the field, and student assistants acquiring practical experience to augment their education at the University.

The CSLab also aims to fully integrate citizen science practices into the University's educational programmes, across all faculties. The current Science Communication and Society curriculum contains course content on citizen science as a practice (SCS Fundamentals), and this will be expanded into other MSc programmes - for example, courses on 'being a Scientist' can introduce CS as a tool for public engagement in research, courses on 'Museums, Cultural Heritage and Collections' can introduce the role of citizen collectors and transcribers, and courses about environmental pollution can introduce CS as a data collection method.

To more deeply embed CS practices, the CSLab will develop a new elective on Citizen Science. In this course, master students will learn about all aspects of citizen science, including suitable research methods, collaboration with citizens and societal organisations, data management, ethical and legal issues, joint benefits, and so on. The CSLab will also develop a cross-faculty Honours College course that focuses on developing citizen science for the Sustainable Development Goals, in collaboration with the Honours Colleges and the Young Academy Leiden.

*"This vision for Europe's universities in 2030 requires a reform of academic careers... incentivising activities with different forms of impact, including innovation or **citizen science**...while retaining the core goal of research activities, which is the expansion of human knowledge;" - A Vision for 2030, European University Association*

Embedding CS into research practices across the University will primarily entail raising awareness of 'the Science of CS' via webinars and lunch presentations and building capacity via workshops and training sessions. The CSLab will support colleagues across the University in embedding citizen engagement and 'burgerparticipatie' practices within their research (particularly in funding proposals where public engagement is a requirement) and will also seek out opportunities to co-develop new transdisciplinary CS research initiatives. Our three main vehicles for achieving this are 'made-to-measure' workshops within specific faculties and institutes, collaborations with our Core Scientific Group of Ambassadors, and active contributions to the eight 'Stimulerend' programmes launched in 2020 to strengthen interdisciplinary collaboration throughout the University in response to major issues affecting the world today.

*"As pluralistic societies come under threat, universities must support civic values through **active engagement**. They can do this by.... promoting opportunities for learners to actively **engage in societal projects**...[and] ...promoting **civic engagement** across the university missions, developing participation, respect for diversity and open debate as a common value across the institution" - A Vision for 2030, European University Association*

To better embed these practices in societal activities within Leiden, we aim to identify and establish a unique physical hub for citizen science in the heart of the city, to function as a 'Loket' for the Participate programme during the European City of Citizen Science Festival (see Goal 2), that can become a permanent location beyond 2022 with facilities for active outreach events, talks, maker spaces, and workshops with residents. An easily accessible central location will be key to building community capacity for co-creation, co-design, and multi-stakeholder collaboration. This CS 'Loket' will operate in close partnership with current initiatives such as the Huis van de Wetenschap, Leren met de Stad, and the 'kenniswinkel' initiative that has been launched with the first location in 'Het Gebouw' in the northern part of Leiden. More ambitiously, this physical hub could be part of a Leiden-wide response to the New European Bauhaus initiative - a vision of the EU to create an interdisciplinary movement that functions as *"...a think-do tank. A design lab, accelerator and network at the same time. A creative and interdisciplinary movement, convening a space of encounter to recuperate and revisit sustainable practices, empower the most inspiring practices of today, and design future ways of living, at the crossroads between art, culture and science"*.

Opportunities to establish such a central physical location include future plans for the Hudson's Bay / V&D building at the buzzing heart of the city (see the ambitions of Stichting StadsLab Leiden), or historical buildings owned by the University in prime locations. With this initiative, the CSLab will establish itself as the central hub for expertise and innovation for citizen science beyond 2022, with an eye on the SDG goals for 2030.

SMART Objectives: By 31/12/2021 run one Citizen Science workshop within each transdisciplinary 'Stimulerend' programme and one 'Citizen Science in Horizon Europe' workshop with the Scientific Core Group; expand the current CS content offered in the Science Communication and Society (MSc) curriculum into at least two other masters programmes; by the end of 2022 develop one new elective on Citizen Science and one cross-faculty Honours College course that focuses on developing citizen science for the Sustainable Development Goals; by the end of 2022 originate and co-develop a minimum of three new CS projects with UL researchers that have local, national and even international reach.

GOAL 5: Establish the CSLab as a cornerstone of the nascent Dutch National Network for Citizen Science

nationaal
programma
**open
science**

On 26 October 2020, the National Program Open Science published the advisory report of the Citizen Science working group - Kennis en krachten gebundeld citizen science in Nederland - for the establishment of a National Citizen Science network, to strengthen innovation, collaboration, and the leading position of the Netherlands in the field of citizen science. Two founding

members of the CSLab took the initiative for these discussions on a national level, and acted as lead authors of the report, setting the ambitions and strategic goals for the network and introducing the Quality Matrix for Citizen Science that is at the heart of the report.

It is the ambition of the CSLab to lead the establishment of the 'Netwerk Citizen Science NL' and make it operational in 2021, and to become a cornerstone of the network over the long term. Our vision is to not only provide a physical hub in Leiden for hosting networking and knowledge exchange events among academic and non-academic stakeholders and partners, but also to become a knowledge hub for Citizen Science expertise, innovation and research in the Netherlands - expanding the Leiden 2022 'Participate' Platform to serve as the national online platform for CS and incubating collaborative transdisciplinary CS projects in member-based consortia.

SMART Objectives: By 31/05/2021 sign Memorandum of Understanding with Universiteit Twente to co-lead the establishment of the 'Netwerk Citizen Science NL', secure funding from the NPOS / KNAW for 0.25 FTE coordination staff to be based in the CSLab.

MISSION:

to be *the* Knowledge Hub, Project Incubator, and Research Centre for citizen science in Leiden and the Netherlands

VISION:

In 2025, Leiden is a pioneer of citizen science that is initiated and carried out jointly by the University and the rest of the city to address urgent scientific and societal challenges.

**citizen
science lab**

Our Growth & Funding Strategy

With foundational ‘seed’ funding to bring in the dedicated focus of a full-time Coordinator, the CSLab is poised for a period of exciting growth, and the delivery of an ambitious strategic vision. This seed funding will have a multiplier effect, that allows the CSLab to attract additional funding for growing both the project portfolio and core staff. This includes securing funding to deliver the ambitious goals for the Leiden 2022 European of City of (Citizen) Science programme, as well as bringing in both national and EU project funding.

SCENARIO GRAPHED	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Permanent Staff FTE	0.475	0.2	0.2	0.15	0.15
CSLab Coordinator FTE	1	1	1	1	1
Project-based personnel FTE	2	7.5	6	7.5	7.5
# projects ECS & NL	2	4	2	2	2
# WP-lead projects EU	2	3	2	1	1
# Coordinated projects EU	0	2	1	1	1

In outlining our growth strategy, there are a number of possible scenarios that depend entirely on our ability to secure funding – which will thus impact the legacy of the Citizen Science Lab beyond 2022 into 2025, 2030, and beyond. Here we illustrate a realistic middle-ground scenario with a peak number of projects during Leiden 2022 (four local & NL, and five EU), and a steady portfolio of 5 projects (ranging from local to EU) going into 2025.

This scenario would allow us to build a strong CSLab team of operational, project and research staff, with the potential to fund one or more PhD students or Postdocs. The graph above describes the Leiden 2022 scenario where the CSLab curates and originates a full-year of CS activities and launches our own flagship ‘CS for the SDGs’ initiative to co-create projects that are scaled across the Netherlands, but does not include the building of an online portal for all ‘Participate’ activities, or the establishment of a physical base for the CSLab at the heart of the city.

Our Structure

The Citizen Science Lab Structure

The Citizen Science Lab is led by a full-time Coordinator and the three founding members of the CSLab, who serve the role of an Executive Board. The team also consists of one full-time PhD researcher and one part-time project officer. The team has a wide national and international CS network, hands-on CS experience, and are active in engaging the public and other stakeholders in CS initiatives, including partnerships with the Municipalities of Leiden and the Hague, Naturalis, and the Lorentz Center.

The Scientific Core Group (as also described above) serve as ambassadors and collaboration partners, connecting the CSLab with all 7 faculties of the University, and the eight interdisciplinary 'Stimulerings' programmes launched in 2020.

The CSLab Network

The Citizen Science Lab is active in networks at multiple levels. At the local level we have close ties with Gemeente Leiden and initiatives such as Leiden Kennisstad, Leren met de Stad, de Wetenschapsknooppunt, and Leiden 4 Global Goals. At the national level we are members of the NPOS Citizen Science Working Group, and together with Universiteit Twente are taking the lead in establishing the 'CS Netwerk NL' according to the recommendations contained in the 2020 strategic report on citizen science (as described in Goal 5). The CSLab also hopes to become the official partner of Stichting Leiden European City of Science 2022 to deliver the 'Participate' programme throughout the year - showcasing both the City of Leiden and the Netherlands on the European stage.

At the European level, CSLab co-founder Anne Land was co-chair of the recently completed Citizen Science COST Action, and the CSLab is a founding member of the application to establish a COST Action for Citizen Science and the SDGs. The CSLab is a member of the European Citizen Science Association, with whom we are partnering to build the EU-Citizen.Science platform, where we also represent CS in the Netherlands within European networks.

At the global level we are actively involved in the CS Global Partnership and its working groups, have frequently been a member of the global Citizen Science delegation to UNEA and the UN Science Policy & Business Fora, and are member of the global CS Data & Metadata Working Group developing a global standard for CS data and metadata (PPSR-Core).

The CSLab Team Members

The CSLab Coordinator

Margaret Gold, MBA

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Margaret Gold joins the Citizen Science Lab to take on the role of Coordinator, and to fill various project roles such as Community Manager (O.2 FTE) for the Netherlands in the Horizon 2020 funded EU-Citizen.science program. Before this, Margaret was working at the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), where she was Project Officer in the WeObserve project, which is consolidating knowledge about citizen observatories for environmental monitoring, the LandSense project, which is a citizen observatory and innovation marketplace for land use and land cover monitoring, and the EU-Citizen.Science project, which is building a platform for sharing citizen science projects, resources, and training in support of the European community of practitioners (both experienced and new, formal and DIY).

Margaret's publications on the role of citizen science in achieving the UN Sustainable Development goals include an extensive mapping paper in Sustainability Science (<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00833-7>), a perspective piece in Nature Sustainability (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0390-3>), and a thorough inventory of citizen science projects that contribute to environmental policy (<https://doi.org/10.2779/961304>). Additionally, Margaret was part of the working group who developed the ECSA Characteristics of Citizen Science (<https://zenodo.org/communities/citsccharacteristics>)

Margaret combines 15 years in the mobile & web technology sector with 10 years of community building in Citizen Science - engaging the public in the transcription of digitally imaged specimen labels at the Natural History Museum in London, and in scientific research within the Citizen Cyberlab project. Margaret has an MBA from the Rotterdam School of Management at Erasmus University in the Netherlands, and an Honours BA in International Relations from the University of Windsor in Canada.

The Founders and CSLab Board

Dr. Anne Land-Zandstra - Faculty of Science, Science Communication & Society

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7604-9092>

Anne Land-Zandstra is Assistant Professor in the Science Communication and Society Group. She specializes in the "Science of Science Communication" specifically for science museums, and the "Science of Citizen Science". Her main interest for the latter is studying the motivations and learning outcomes of participants in citizen science projects. She has made essential contributions to large citizen science projects like De Grote Griepmeting, iSPEX, and Schone Rivieren by performing and analysing project evaluations.

Anne actively applies her experience from these and other projects to new projects at the earliest stages of project conception and co-creation. She has been a founding member of the Citizen Science Lab, and applies her expertise to all the CSLab's projects, and supervises MSc/PhD students that support and study these projects during their life cycles.

Anne is a member of the National Platform Open Science working group on Citizen Science and leads the development of a new quality matrix for the design and assessment of new citizen science projects. Anna is Vice-Chair COST action 15212 "Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe".

Dr. ir. Frans Snik - Faculty of Science, Sterrewacht

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Frans Snik is Assistant Professor at Leiden Observatory where he leads a group that develops advanced optical instrumentation for both astronomy as well as remote sensing of Earth. In his ERC Starting Grant Project FALCONER he develops novel techniques to enable the direct observation of planets orbiting other stars than the Sun from telescopes all over the globe and in

space. Technology invented by Frans Snik is currently being built into the SPEXone instrument for the next NASA climate satellite PACE (by Airbus in Leiden) to provide unique and urgent measurements of the influence of anthropogenic aerosols on our climate and on our health.

As a spin-off from the development towards SPEXone, Frans Snik led the development of iSPEX; an optical add-on for smartphones that enables citizen scientists to perform measurements of air pollution. After winning the Academische Jaarprijs in 2012, the first major iSPEX citizen science experiment was organized in the Netherlands in 2013, with several thousand participants demonstrating the viability of the measurement concept, and also of the pioneering citizen science approach. In 2015, iSPEX was implemented in 10 major cities all across Europe. iSPEX also led to the development of the Citizen Science Lab, initially to fulfil a demand to provide expertise to other scientists with an interest in citizen science. In collaboration with the colleagues led below,

Frans Snik is a member of the Dutch Young Academy (De Jonge Akademie) and is as such actively involved in new national policies regarding interdisciplinarity, and specifically citizen science (NPOS working group on Citizen Science) and art+science collaborations (Academy of Arts working group).

Dr. Pedro Russo - Faculty of Science, Sterrewacht, Science Communication & Society

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8589-7800>

Pedro Russo is Assistant Professor at the SCS Department, Leiden University, and the coordinator of the Astronomy & Society group of Leiden Observatory. Russo is the principal investigator for H2020 spaceEU and H2020 Open Science Hub Network projects. Pedro has been involved in several Citizen Science initiatives, from Professional and Amateurs collaborations in Astronomy to the development of the citizen-science iPhone application Dark Sky Meter - Cosmic Light Edition. As a founding member of the Citizen Science Lab, Pedro has been using Community-Based Participatory Research approaches in Citizen-Science, like the development of the CSLab-44 project Plastic Spotter.

Pedro is involved with several international organisations, like the European Astronomical Society, Europlanet (European Planetology Network), the International Astronautical Federation. His work has received several awards, such as Seeds Special Award 2009, Scientix Best Educational Resource in 2015 and 2016, Most Innovative Educational Activities in 2017 and 2018 by HundrED and 2018 Leiden University's K.J. Cath Prize.

Members of the CSLab

Liselotte Rambonnet MSc - Faculty of Science, Science Communication & Society

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Liselotte Rambonnet is a PhD student in the Science Communication & Society Group, specifically studying the motivations, expectations and impact of citizen scientists. She is an active member of

the Citizen Science Lab and acted as CSLab Project Manager and Community Manager for the UL444 projects Plastic Spotter and Psychology Lab on Wheels during 2019. Liselotte brought together many local stakeholders and implemented and evaluated the new co-creation methods that led to these two new projects. Liselotte is also actively involved in the European Horizon 2020 projects SciShops.eu and EU-Citizen.Science. Moreover, Liselotte is the co-initiator of Canal Cups, which has led to the ban on single-use plastic cups during large events in Leiden.

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Maria Vicente is the Project Manager of the H2020 Open Science Hub project, at Leiden University. Maria holds a PhD in Neuroscience and was responsible for the Science Education programme at the Champalimaud Centre for the Unknown, Lisbon, Portugal. Since 2017, she has been the Scientific Coordinator of Open Science Hub – Portugal, aimed at bringing together science, technology and innovation with the daily-life of local communities, with a strong focus on Open Schooling and Social Innovation. Currently, Maria is the Project Manager of the H2020 Open Science Hub project, which is establishing 8 community hubs across Europe, near social and/or geographical borders, to engage schools in tackling challenges faced by their local communities, supporting them to become active agents for collaboration between civil society, enterprises, research institutes, families and the local community.

The Scientific Core Group

The Scientific Core Group of the CSLab brings in scientific subject-matter expertise via an Ambassador from each of the faculties of the University, to serve as advisors, supporters and partners of the CSLab.

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Thijs Bosker	Faculty of Science	Sietse Wieringa	Leiden University Medical Center
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